

BARRIERS FOR ONLINE AND OFFLINE CORPORATE COMMUNICATION. CASE STUDY: ORGANIZATIONAL COMMUNICATION IN TIMISOARA

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Abstract

Purpose: *The research questions of the present study are: “how can we transmit information from a source to the destination with a minimum of distortions and errors in an organization?” and “how can communication fight against changes and problems in an organization?” The topic is relevant in the pandemic context, where significant changes in organizational communication have been implemented.*

Methodology: *For answering the two research questions, a Grounded Theory approach has been chosen. In the initial phase 15 semi-structured interviews have been implemented on an heterogenous group of employees from the private sector in the Western part of Romania, with a minimum work experience of at least three years. The open coding process with constant comparison of information determined interrelated categories. In the end, based on literature argumentation, the final theoretical model regarding the elements of corporate communication barriers has been delineated.*

Findings: *The main findings are: formal communication is considered a communication barrier because it assigns different “tags” to employees in a company. Also, online communication is considered beneficial if offline communication exists. Many respondents believe that communication during the pandemic period made it difficult to understand the message due to a lack of non-verbal communication and active listening.*

Research limitations: *Interviews were only given by employees in large companies (corporations) because in small and medium-sized companies we cannot outline the topic of research. The limited number of interviews of employees situated in the Western part of Romania limits the generalization of results for other regions. Further studies will focus on larger samples of employees from all the regions of Romania and even abroad.*

Practical implication: *With the help of the qualitative research undertaken, the main communication barriers in large organizations during the COVID pandemic have been emphasized, being a starting point for designing new corporate strategies to systematically eliminate them.*

Originality: *There are no qualitative studies on this topic carried out in the Western part of Romania. The proposed theoretical model represents the basis for efficient corporate communication post COVID decision making and strategic thinking.*

Key words: COVID-19 , Grounded Theory, organizational communication, bureaucracy, organizational culture, formalism

Introduction

The pandemic crisis has imposed many changes in the industry at all levels. The current paper focuses on changes in organizational communication because it represents the „foundation of modern organizations” (Grenier, 2000). This topic has been of great interest for scholars (Allen et. Al, 1993, Kain Sanders et. Al, 2020, Heri Erlanga et Al. 2020). Along the last decade, managers had to deal with new government regulations, increased competition, technological developments, changing work force needs (Lewis et Al. 1998) and during the last two years a worldwide pandemic.

With the pandemic, “all business life has moved online, and business has started to run remotely” (Eastwood, 2021a, p.198). The pandemic crisis has also generated, what Lindstrom (2020, p.168) calls “safety madness” in organizations because “all emails start and end with “being healthy” or “being safe”.

Also, as Guda (2018) expressed, “the negative changes in the lives of employees are often dramatic for companies...because the human psyche influences the mission and vision of a company”.

All these changes in organizational communication need to be studied because “employees are the most important asset of the organization” (Mayo, 2001).

There has been a growing academic interest in different forms of companies and employees. For example, organizational behavior and employees’ motivation occupies an important place in recent years studies (Nyberg et al, 2021, Putra et Al. 2021, Tang et Al. 2022). Other researchers have turned their attention to leadership or changes that occur in organizations Serra et al, 2021).

The present study focuses on organizational communication in a pandemic and “post-pandemic period”. About the role of organizational communication in the pandemic crisis Zito et al. (2021) claims that “the role of communication in this reorganization is very important because it can reduce technostress and psycho-physical disorders highlighting the importance of clear information and engaging situations”. Also, Van Zoonen et al.(2021) declare that “crisis has disrupted when, where, and how employees work”.

Therefore, the research questions are:

1. how can we transmit information from a source to the destination with a minimum of distortions and errors in an organization?
2. how can communication fight against changes and problems in a corporate environment?

The research questions are designed to outline the current barriers of organizational communication. For this purpose, the qualitative Grounded theory approach has been chosen based on in-depth interviews with corporate employees.

Methodology

Grounded theory (GT) it is a qualitative method of research, and qualitative analysis of data means to manages words, language, and the meanings these imply (Miles Huberman, 1994). Grounded theory emerged in the 1960s as a result of Glaser and Strauss’s sociological research program and the “magnificence of this theory exists in its capacity to create rich descriptions and understandings of social life”. (Walker, Myrick, 2006a).

The method contains 3 phases as research called: the open phase, axial coding and selective coding. In the first phase, open coding, analysts immerse themselves in the data through line-by-line analysis, “coding the data is an many ways as possible and writing memos about the conceptual and theoretical ideas that emerge during the course of analysis” (Walker, Myrick, 2006b).

The second phase of the method consists of axial data coding. At this stage, the methods uses two keys concepts: code and coding. Glaser has described the code as “the essential relationship between data and theory” and coding as a process that, “gets the analyst off the empirical level by fracturing the data, then conceptually grouping it into codes that then become the theory which explains what is happening in the data” (Glaser, 1978a).

The third phase is the process of using selective codes to “conceptualize how the substantive codes may relate to each other as hypotheses to be integrated into a theory”. (Glaser, 1978b).

Thus, through this study we collected information, which we later coded and analyzed to better understand the communication barriers that exist in 3 of the largest companies in Timisoara. All the information collected followed the analysis process described in figure 1.

To find out the main problems of organizational communication from the point of view of employees, we collected data from 15 subjects. The 15 subjects were chosen with ages ranging from 23 till 34, both male and female with a minimum of 3 years of experience on the labor market at companies in Timisoara. The time that data was collected from the subjects is 2 months, and the time allocated to meetings with them was 22,5 hours.

Figure 1.

The interview guide was built upon 17 open questions, starting with introductory questions about professional area of expertise, projects and interests followed by specific, direct and projective questions regarding the organizational communication concept.

The interviews have been placed over a period of three months, in which the interviewees were contacted by e-mail and asked if they are interested to schedule a meeting at their workplace or online using the “Zoom” platform. The place of the interview was chosen according to the preferences of each subject to facilitate the research time. Most interviews were conducted via the internet. Each interview was recorded with the consent of the subjects, respecting the law of private data. For each subject, we have used its initials. Each interview recording was fully transcribed for data analysis.

The analysis began by transcribing all interviews in chronological order. For each interview, specific codes for the main notions of interest were assigned. After establishing the codes, a memo was made at each interview that briefly describes the essence of the interview. The coding process was performed according to the three stages described by Glaser (1978c): open phase, axial coding and selective coding.

The open coding phase comprises a total number of 15 memos which contain 113 concepts. The number of concepts indicates that the subjects had common views about the topic of research. It continues with an axial coding stage where initial codes have been explored to reveal which of them best cover the ideas drawn from collected data. In this stage, 6 main categories based on the 113 codes were highlighted. To choose the 6 main categories, we looked at which of these are repetitive in the interviews of the subjects. The 6 categories contain 4-5 subcodes.

The selective coding represents the last step towards a first sketch of the theoretical model of barriers of organizational communication. It explores the relations between categories in the search of the core category to which all the codes will furthermore relate to. For a better understanding of the codes, we made a graph presented in figure 2.

Figure 2

Data analysis and literature review/confrontation

Figure 3 shows the core of the 6 identified categories, namely “organizational communication barriers”. The core is closely related to the six categories called: large volume of information, poor listening, formalism, bureaucracy, professional affinities, and organizational culture. The 6 categories are called “super categories” because they include other groups of categories identified by the analysis. As can be seen in the table shown in figure 3, a hierarchy of the most important categories has been realized together with their distribution in six specific groups called 'super categories'.

Super categories	Information overload	Poor listening	Formalism	Bureaucracy	Professional affinities	Organizational culture
Initial categories						
1	wasted time	ego	status	limited time	groups	language barriers
2	lack of efficacy	anxiety	lack of respect	Lack of simplicity	lack of help	values
3	disorganization	tone of voice	hesitations	hasty	tags	job description
4	meetings	individualism	pressure	insecurity	assumptions	
5	burnout	non-verbal language	Lack of transparency	technical problems	reputation	
6		remote job				

Figure 3

According to the table, the large amount of information is the main communication barrier in organizations. Employees of companies think they are wasting time on tasks to attend too many meetings. The “poor listening” category represents the second communication barrier in organizations. The lack of active listening shapes an individualistic employee whose ego hinders the efficiency of organizational communication.

An interesting category is formalism. According to the analysis, the only function of formalism is to shape the hierarchy in companies. Paradoxically, formal communication is no longer an indicator of respect.

The 5th category is called professional affinities because the social life of companies is affected by assumptions and groups that lead to lack of help between employees. Moreover, the organizational culture of companies affects organizational communication because it exists only on a theoretical level.

All 6 categories are analyzed below by confronting the literature together with the interviews given.

Information overload

According to Bowden and Robinson, the information is increasing due to the “evolution of online technologies” (2021a). Lindstrom argues that too much information that flows through “rules, laws, regulations, description of company trips or future plans of the organization” creates an entanglement that will no longer be the company’s promoter (2021a). It is also believed that with the popularity of online tools, information is transmitted more easily, but there is a risk of not wanting to receive information (Bowden, Robinson 2021b).

The subjects consider that: the main cause of burnout is too much information they receive. In literature, workplace burnout is fundamental crisis in the psychological connections that people establish with work (Rozman, 2018).

Active listening in organizations is “the creation and implementation of processes and systems that enable decision makers...to actively and effectively access, acknowledge, understand, and consider and appropriately respond to all those who wish to communicate” (Macnamara, 2016a).

According to the employees interviewed because of the sudden change in the working environment, human relationships have weakened, increasing social anxiety, and each employee is concerned about himself. About remote work, Ye believes that the speed of response and the option to be able to communicate with anyone and anytime are the main drivers of successful communication mediated by the computer. However, remote communication leads to “difficulty building trusting, missing out on small talk and sometimes even critical conversations, and feeling isolated”. (Rice-Bailey, 2014).

The literature states that the problems of active listening can fade if “an organizational culture is open to listening” (Macnamara, 2016b) and organizations must apply the “skip-level” meetings (Neil, 2021a). However, the subjects claim that the meetings “one by one” with the manager are superficial. Moreover, most of these meetings take place online and each employee is “more busy solving technical problems than paying attention to the discussion.”

To shape a good relationship between employees and the organization, Neil says managers should provide to employees “opportunities to speak out, get involved, be listened to, and actively participate” (2021). But the problem of active listening according to coding is related to social anxiety and sudden social changes in organizations. Thus, one of the subjects considered “during the period leading up to the pandemic, colleagues at work were more interested in listening to you.”

The bureaucracy in organizations received limited attention in the communication and management literature. Of the organizational bureaucracy, he states that it must “be aimed at making the lives of employment easier” (2016). However, company employees say that bureaucracy limits working time and causes them to stop resorting to “official steps to solve problems”.

Almaarif approaches organizational bureaucracy in close connection with organizational culture. He argues that organizations choose and continue to apply traditional models of organizational culture at a time of evolution. (2021)

Formalism

The formalism of organizational communication is not one of the broad topics of research. However, employees consider it an impediment to communication because you cannot express yourself freely, and everything that is transmitted can be interpreted by desolating the fear of communicating. About the fear of communicating, Lindstrom says that “there are many unwritten rules in organizations ... that everyone follows just to be respected,” and through this method employees live in fear because the organization’s culture is based on fear (2021b).

Formal communication is. Although one of the functions of formal communication is to “show respect for the interlocutor,” paradoxically the subjects consider it “a form of shaping the organizational hierarchy.”

According to the coding process, formal communication in organizations and to whom you address determines how much respect a colleague deserves. Thus, subjects prefer informal communication or a mixed communication model to be applied.

Professional affinities

Professional affinities refer to groups that form between employees. These groups are referred to by Eastwood as “the organization’s gangs” (2021b). They occur naturally, from the desire of people to feel that they “belong to a collective in a potentially intimidating environment” (Dunbar, 2019, p.173). However, professional affinities pose a risk to organizations because “they fragment a team and distort its activity.”(Eastwood, 2021c)

The analysis identified two consequences of group formation in the workplace: Assumptions and labels.

Organizational culture

Organizational culture is one of the most important factors influencing a company’s human resource because “without the guidelines of a strong culture ... natural patterns inevitably come into play” (Rinata, Putra, Goh, 2022). The term “organizational culture” has been given many definitions, and Table 1 shows examples of this. Although organizational culture is found in every company through its vision, mission and values, the major problem is that many companies turn organizational culture into a corporate law. (Lindstrom,2021d) this error in the practice of organizations often starts from those who have to ensure the visibility of organizational culture – managers, department heads, CEO.

Thus, the errors of the organizational culture were also highlighted by the interview analysis. The subjects claim that “companies do not rush their own values”. Some respondents also believe that organizations are not sincere with the information they provide in the job description, although “this is the first stage of the employee-organization relationship”(Neil, 2021b).

Barriers of organizational communication – a Theoretical Model

Following the analysis of the codes, we set out to develop a model of the barriers of organizational communication. For a better understanding, they are shown in Figure 4.

Thus, according to the confrontation of the literature with the codes obtained from the interviews, we can create a model of the communication barriers, outlining the relationships between them.

Figure 4

The literature claims that organizational culture is the failure or success of a company (Mayo, 2014). In this way, organizational culture is the barrier to communication that influences all other barriers to organizational communication. Also, according to researchers Rinata et Al, employees are not made to listen (2022), and Guimera et al. Alma’rif argues that organizational culture is given from generation to generation (2021b).

In addition, company employees will always seek to build small groups “that will provide them with alliances that could provide more protection and stability” (Eastwood, 2021), and companies will want their employees to comply with the same unchanged rules and poorly defined values (Lindstrom,2021).

Thereby, companies need to improve the organizational culture that directly influences both employees and their way of working. Also, in a post-pandemic period, the disadvantages of working from home must be analyzed.

The theoretical model shown in Figure 4 can be applied as a corporation's "analysis sheet" to analyze its strengths and weaknesses. Thus, with the help of this theoretical model we can answer the proposed questions. First, we can send a message with a minimum of distortion to an organization if we first identify the distortions to be eliminated or blurred. The analysis also outlines that organizational communication can help combat change only if the communication mode integrates the preferences of the company's employees.

Conclusions

According to the literature of specificity and the analysis carried out with the help of the Grounded theory, the main communication barriers of three of the companies in Timisoara were identified. Considering that such a study has not been conducted in Timisoara, we consider that the research carried out is a first step in shaping a new model of organizational communication.

According to the code, organizational communication must have new valences such as: A mixed mode of communication in order to avoid “excessive formalism”, work from the office to return, organizational culture to be innovated, and affinities between employees can exist as long as it does not affect the mission of the organization.

Also, all of these barriers to organizational communication have emerged due to the pandemic crisis, so organizations need to adjust communication and organizational culture according to employees and the new social reality.

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